

Archaeology of the invisible (Archaia)

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1. Introduction: The Hole and “Murakami” Experience

In this thesis paper I will try to articulate the theoretical process behind the concept of my Master’s final photographic project “Archaia”. For this, I will part from the starting point of the project, the real “facts”, passing through theories about the contemplation of trauma and the act of remembering as seen in photography and art; and the relationship between photography and archeology, in which I would like to question the added value of “truth” within photography.

I also wanted to see if, in the context of a family memory, photographs tend to be more than just proves and reminders, but also hints, pointers to psychological wounds. Wounds that do not heal but are rather unconsciously transported in the family communication rather than deliberately handed down. My first question was, to which extent, the unwanted/involuntary repetition of a visual remembrance related to a traumatic experience could help to or wether make it more problematic to process that trauma, but when I started my research I realised that I was not a psychologist nor a scientist, so I couldn’t really answer that question. So I decided to focus on the visual aspect of those topics related to photography. By that many questions arouse, like for example how is photography related to the trauma theory? How are collective traumatic memories represented in art? How is the photographic latency related to psychological processes and how can I show it in my project? What happens to the memories of stories which can only remain through photographs as the only witnesses? And where relies the truth in those photographs?

When I started with this project I just didn’t want to tell a story. I wanted to create something, based on real historical facts, that could make a change in how that story is perceived. After some time working on it, maybe a year, I realised that I couldn’t work anymore on it and that I had to make a break, I had to go to the depths of darkness to be able to see again. There was an existential moment happening that made me realise that, when I read a passage of Haruki Murakami’s book “The wind-up bird”, where the protagonist

decides to stay in the bottom of a dry well in order to be able to think. Mr. Okada, the protagonist of the book, was going through a harsh time in his life, as he had just discovered that his wife had disappeared and had been having an affair with another man. It is for this reason that he decided to go down on a dry well, with nothing but a torch, a ladder, a wristwatch and some water.

Down there, in the darkness, he started to go out of himself and think. Like in meditation, it was an attempt to escape from reality, being in a hole, completely isolated from the world, away from any possible interaction with anything. He realised that just there, in that complete darkness, he was capable to reflect:

“I sat in the dark. Far above me, like a sign of something, floated the perfect half-moon of light given shape by the well cap. And yet none of the light from up there managed to find its way to the bottom.

As time passed, my eyes became more accustomed to the darkness. Before long, I could just barely make out the shape of my hand if I brought it close to my face. Other things around me began slowly to take on their own dim shapes, like timid little animals letting down their guard in the most gradual stages imaginable. As much as my eyes became used to it, though, the darkness never ceased to be darkness. Anything I tried to focus on would lose its shape and burrow its way soundlessly into the surrounding obscurity. Perhaps this could be called “pale darkness,” but pale as it might be, it had its own particular kind of density, which in some cases contained a more deeply meaningful darkness than perfect pitch darkness. In it, you could see something. And at the same time, you could see nothing at all.

Here in this darkness, with its strange sense of significance, my memories began to take on a power they had never had before. The fragmentary images they called up inside me were mysteriously vivid in every detail, to the point where I felt I could grasp them in my hands. I closed my eyes and brought

back the time eight years earlier when I had first met Kumiko.”¹

[...] “I was crouching down in the total darkness. All I could see was nothingness. And I was part of this nothingness. I closed my eyes and listened to the sound of my heart, to the sound of the blood circulating through my body, to the bellows-like contractions of my lungs, to the slippery undulations of my food-starved gut. In the deep darkness, every movement, every throb, was magnified enormously. This was my body, my flesh. But in the darkness, it was all too raw and physical. Soon my conscious mind began to slip away from my physical body. I saw myself as the wind-up bird, flying through the summer sky, lighting on the branch of a huge tree somewhere, winding the world’s spring. If there really was no more wind-up bird, someone would have to take on its duties. Someone would have to wind the world’s spring in its place. Otherwise, the spring would run down and the delicately functioning system would grind to a halt. The only one who seemed to have noticed that the wind-up bird was gone, however, was me.”²

At first I felt very identified with this story, as I had recently started to feel like in an inspirational crisis with my photographic work. I had the feeling that I was also in a “dark well”, or better, in a black hole, not physically but emotionally. I also felt the necessity to distance myself from the topic, as it was coming from a personal and familiar story, and that it was resulting too emotional for me and for the spectator. But at some point I also realised that I actually needed to be in that “black hole” so that I could be able to rethink my project and come with new perspectives.

An art professor at university told me once: “When you realise that you are in the hole, you are already a bit out of it”, in which she meant that an inspiration crisis within an artistic process is important, and also, necessary. It is good to stop with everything hat

1 Murakami, Haruki: *The wind-up bird*, Japan, 1994. p. 312

2 Ibid.

one has been creating till that moment, maybe also to throw it out, and start anew from another point. So I accepted my hole and embraced it, and from that moment I started to come out of it.

2. The starting point: a place called Mansilla de la Sierra

2.1. The story of the two villages

I've known the story of the village Mansilla de la Sierra since I was a child. My grandfather and other family members, as my mother, were born there. But I always had the feeling that in my family we never talked about what had happened there.

During the sixties, many water reservoirs were built all around Spain under the Franco Dictatorship. These villages were evacuated, for there there was a dam being built that stopped the water of the rivers bathing that valley. An artificial swamp was thus created, to provide water for the country, for consumption and irrigation. And so the villages and all the valley where they were situated became flooded.

The inhabitants of these villages, assumingly, were not very happy about this, as they had to leave their homes and everything they possessed as stables, orchards, businesses, etc. Some new villages were built, to offer a new place to live for the inhabitants of those places. In the case of Mansilla, the new village was built just two kilometres away. From this location, placed on the mountainside, the water reservoir was always visible.

The plans of Franco were actually to offer these people a new house in the Monegros region, as a compensation for their loss, where they could work on the farming of the lands. Franco wanted to bring people there, as they were empty lands, but these lands were also deserts, so no one wanted actually to move there. Franco had made many new villages in Spain during the sixties through the "Instituto Nacional de Colonización" (National Colonisation Institute). These villages were settled in inhabited landscapes, and he offered a house as a "gift" to the inhabitants that would come there to work on the land. That land was normally barren, so the people had to work a long time on it till it gave some crop. In exchange, besides getting a house, the people had to give the Government a percentage of their harvest.

From the almost 500 inhabitants that Mansilla had in 1950, only 149 decided to move to the new village that had been built. In the moment these people arrived to the new villages, there was no running water or electricity in the houses. Most of them had to pay for this new houses, as they had lost the right on a compensation, because the houses in the flooded village weren't registered on their names (in the past, it was not always ordinary to transfer the registration of the houses when being inherited) and they didn't want to move to the Monegros desert region. Now there are 55 people officially registered in the new Mansilla, but in winter only 12 really live there. The village is disappearing slowly, if it was not for the tourists coming in the summer time.

2.2. Mansilla in the literature

At the starting point of my research, I began reading the books that talked about similar stories to this one. There is a relevant spanish writer, Ana Maria Matute, who actually had spent all the summers of her childhood in the old Mansilla. In a book called "El río" (The River), she tells about her experiences there, how it looked like, what she did with other children, which places they were around, etc. One can imagine very easily after her narrative how the life looked there back then. One can also feel the sadness of losing that place, and how it felt when it disappeared below the water:

“After eleven years, I have returned to Mansilla de la Sierra, the landscape of my childhood. The swamp has already covered the old town, and a group of white houses, too new and astonished, glow in the humid green of autumn. After so much time, returning to the old landscape removes and revives the blurred images, apparently forgotten, that jump before us with a strange current meaning, and sometimes pathetic. But everything is drowned, living and drowned at the same time, under that layer of dark green glass, which prevents me from moving towards the slope of the forests of Aranguencia, Ombrihuelas, where I loved the beech trees, the oaks. The water covers what were beautiful and sweet riversides, lined with poplars. Opposite from there, on the

other side of the swamp, are the trees, the leaves that saw us as children and teenagers play. The water covers now everything: the ghost of the house, the stone walls, the meadow, the garden, the poplar fields ... How many names, how many children laughter, already silenced. [...]

And the river, how has it disappeared so strangely? I remember the river, limiting the meadow, with its wide slabs covered with lichen and moss; the tender reeds, the white, purple and yellow flowers, the small “soap plants”, the dragonflies that became phosphorescent in the sun; the dark pools under the slanted trees, lame bridges over the water. We knew that the river overflowed sometimes, in the winter, and that it demolished stretches of the stone wall. But we never saw it that way, surpassed, as he fled. I know that river is formed again below. I have read his name, I have heard it under a bridge, already in the plain, between the orchards and the fertile land of La Rioja. But it is not our river, it is not the one we knew. It is not the one who ran and took

our voices, the one who robbed us, more than once, downstream, the handkerchief or the sandal. I don't know where his green and gold water went, his shady fishes, his banks invaded with mint. They say it is there, where the water has widened, taking a thick dye the colour of fear, and flooding everything. But I don't understand these things. At the bottom of the swamp will still live that river. And, closing my eyes, I see it intact as a miracle. A river of gold that runs to a place where it doesn't come back, like life.”³

What is actually also interesting is that the river from which Ana María Matute writes, still goes through the same riverbed at the old village, still going under the bridges (or the ruins that are left from them), after sixty years being covered by the water.

Also Julio Llamazares, another important Spanish writer came from another village that ran the same fate, also being covered by water. In his novel “*Distintas formas de mirar el agua*” (Different ways to look at water) he tells us about how his family confronted this incident, especially from the memories of his father, who was actually the most attached person to that place as he had lived there his whole life and declined to admit the fact that his past was gone. In this passage he describes the moment they left the village and arrived to the new built one:

“It does not surprise me that my mother got emotional every time she sees these mountains, and much more today, that we came here for this purpose. It also happens to me, even if I hadn't seen them again since I was sixteen, from the moment we moved to Palencia.

I remember it as if it were today. I remember the farewells of the neighbours who still resisted in Ferreras waiting for the closure of the dam to throw them out, something that was announced for very soon (they had already cut down all the trees and said they were going to cut the light), and the departure from the house in that truck in which the whole family went besides the animals

3 Matute Ausejo, A. M. ; *The river*, Barcelona, Editorial Destino, 1963

and our belongings. Like the gypsies, my mother said when she saw other neighbours of the town leave for their destination before we seconded *them*. On the eve of our march I remember it also clearly. With everything already collected, prepared and stacked in the corral along with the tools and some farming tools (we could not all carry them), the house looked like a warehouse in which our voices echoed. We all slept in the kitchen. My parents on a mattress on the floor, with Virginia and Augustine between them, and Toño and I in the seat. Before we had dinner at Aunt Balbina's house (how soon they would die!) And after dinner we passed through the three houses that were still open to say goodbye to those who stayed. Anyway, the next day, in the morning, everyone was in front of our house to help us carry things and to say goodbye when we finally left. It was a scene that was repeated often in those days and whose image sometimes turns me into dreams filling me with pain, as will happen, I imagine, to the Jews who survived the Nazi concentration camps in World War II.

What awaited us at the end of the trip, which lasted practically the whole day (the roads were not like those of nowadays), was not a concentration camp, but it looked like it. Those uralite barracks that had raised to welcome us while our homes were being built seemed to me, without having seen them yet (i hadn't had the pleasure to be at the cinema yet, neither had I seen any television), pavilions of a concentration camp rather than places where we could live with dignity. In the same way that the image of my father locking our house in Ferrera with the key and keeping it in my pocket when we finished loading everything (as if I did not know that in a short time the water was going to bury it) returned me to memory when I read that some Spanish Jews, when they had to go into exile, kept their house keys in Spain for generations in case they were allowed to return one day. ⁴⁴

4 Llamazares, Julio: *Distintas formas de mirar el agua*, Spain, Penguin Random House, 2015

Llamazares also wrote about another important issue in Spain which is also quite relevant in these times and that is also happening to the new village of Mansilla: the rural depopulation. It is also the case of the village Ainielle, in process of abandonment, which story he tells in his novel “La lluvia amarilla” (The yellow rain):

“While Gavin and Julio remained in Ainielle, the three of us fought together to prevent the people from succumbing to their abandonment ahead of time. Gavín was alone, without family, but with Julio we still followed his two children and his brother and, among all, we cleaned the dams, cleared the orchards and the streets, we recomposed the walls and the palisades or, even, sometimes, we stabbed the beams and we would revoke the cracks in the houses that were beginning to be threatened with ruin. They were difficult years, full of loneliness and hopelessness. But, also, and perhaps for themselves, years that awakened in us a sense of solidarity and friendship that until then we ignored. We were all known of our helplessness in the face of the rage of time and winter on the mountain, we met alone and forgotten in the middle of a land that no one was travelling and that same helplessness brought us closer and united us even more than friendship and blood. The three of us helped each other at work, shared the past that were before all the neighbours and, at night, after having dinner, we all met in the same house to spend the night by the fire chatting and remembering.”⁵

All these three books helped me to understand better the people who had lived that experience, also to fill the gaps of information which my family couldn't contribute with, and to give me a direction on how I could interpret those feelings.

2.3. A visual reminder that is constantly involuntarily repeated

Another interesting fact from this reservoir is that, normally, in the autumn time, the water of the reservoir sinks, because it has been spent through the year for consumption or for

5 Llamazares, Julio: *La lluvia amarilla*, Spain, Planeta, 1999

irrigation. Thereby, the ruins of the old Mansilla reappear, as if it would be a ghost village, and one can see them and even walk through them. The principal flowing river to it, the Gatón river, is even still going through the same riverbed and going under the bridges that still remain, as it did sixty years ago. As if it were a joke from the past, the ruins reappear as if they didn't want to be forgiven.

Through the climate change and due to the drought, the period that the reservoir is empty lasts longer each year. We could also think about a future state where there might be no more water in the reservoir, so the ruins would stay permanently at sight. This would cause their slow total destruction, and at some point, there will be no remains at all. Everything that would stay as a witness from this village would be the photographs that testify its existence. It is for this reason that photography is the best medium with which I can realise this project, because everything will disappear, but there might be photographs, or photographs of photographs that will remain as witnesses. And also because photography allows me to stage my own interpretation of the facts, as I will explain later in the chapter about Post-Memory.

2.4. The Trauma Theory

I've always been familiar with the story of Mansilla, and always had the feeling that my family and the villagers that I talked to didn't really want to talk about it. That is why I started from the idea that there was a trauma involved, and I started to focus on the psychological effects of traumatic experiences like this. What most interested me at first was the fact that in this case there is always a visual material remembrance that is constantly involuntarily repeated, that appears when the ruins of the old village reappear. Also the fact alone that the water reservoir is always visible from the new Mansilla works for me close enough to a reminder of what happened there and what lays below the water.

I also found a relation between the figure of the "hole" (mentioned in the previous chapter, about the Murakami' experience) to one of the topics of my project, the memory process, and the psychological trauma, because a "black hole" in memory can represent a con-

scious repression of memories due to a traumatic experience that wants to be forgotten.⁶ At some point I realised that there were a lot of pictures of black holes or shadows in my photographic series, and wondered if photographing these motifs had something to do with the fact that at that point I was thinking mostly on the psychological effects of the story. In addition, when I started my research and asked about it to my family and the few witnesses that were still alive, I noticed that they had a subtle objection to talk about it. As my aunt told me, that story was a very sad chapter from their lives, it was for them as if the water reservoir would have been a monster that took everything away, and they couldn't understand why I wanted to do this project. This is the reason why I assumed that there was still an unresolved trauma, and I had the chance to dig into the story and find out.

Psychoanalysis and the Trauma Theory were developed by Sigmund Freud in the end of the 19th Century. The notion of "Trauma" began to be accepted in the scientific and also in the general language usage. From the turn of the century around 1900, the photographic and the mnemonic processes would become paralleled which means that Photography made it into the discourse about memory. As the Trauma Theory also copes with the memory performance copes, there is an intersection there from both disciplines.

Freud used photography to illustrate the relationship between consciousness and unconsciousness. As I read in an excerpt of a text about Psychoanalysis,

"A psychic trauma could be defined as an event that, due to its suddenness and intensity, causes the psychological processing capabilities of a person to exceed. The event itself does not have a traumatising effect, but rather the experience triggered thereby and the associated sensory overload. In this respect, an event is always traumatic only in its relation to a sentient subject with its individual stimulus threshold. Traumatic experiences are associated with absolute helplessness and despair, often with dread - feelings so over-

6 McNally, R.J. *The Science and Folklore of Traumatic Amnesia. Clinical Psychology Science and Practice. 11 (1)*, 2004, p. 29–33.

whelming that they threaten to destroy the person. In a kind of emergency response is therefore often first the emotionally reduced excessive demands by “turning off” the feelings.

The most important mental processing for weakening the emotional power of the trauma is repetition, for example in nightmares. Repetition has the function to relive the overwhelming experience to a lesser extent so often, until the trauma can be integrated. The structural transformation of what is actually passively suffered into something actively produced stabilises the ego of the traumatised. Thus, overcoming overpowering can gradually restore self-determination, a process that can take many years.”⁷

From the excerpt we could suppose that actually the fact of repetition would help to recover from a traumatic experience. But as in the case of this ruins, they reappear, unintentionally, so I do not know if we can also apply this theory in this case.

In any case, the repetition in psychotherapy as a tool to work on trauma, and the use of photographs to recall the traumatic events, were both things that were interesting as to my visualisation of the psychological aspect of the story.

“And as the human eye has to get used slowly and steadily, be it to clarity, be it to darkness, so also does the soul has to get used with patience and appropriate successive steps to the domain of the entity, to which she is exposed.”⁸

I found this passage about Plato’s doctrine of truth from Martin Heidegger very interesting, as it also speaks about darkness and clarity, the truth and the beliefs and the human condition. This passage helped me understand why my family didn’t want to talk about what had happened and why they didn’t understand the reason why I make this project.

7 Lorke, Beate: *Jenseits des Lustprinzips*, Leipzig, Internationaler Psychoanalytischer Verlag, 1988.. Ehlert, M. & Lorke, B: *Zur Psychodynamik der traumatischen Reaktion*. *Psyche*, 42, 502–532.

8 Heidegger, Martin: “Plato’s doctrine about the truth”, Institute of Philosophy of the University of Buenos Aires, Notebooks of Philosophy, Fascicle VII, 1953

It also made me consider that probably, in an unconscious way, I am just trying to bring clarity to the history of my family and the people from that village. And so I came to the following question: Do we actually need darkness to be able to get clarity or does darkness help us to cope with reality? In my case, it actually helped me to be in the “black hole” for almost a year. I started to hate my pictures, wanted to start anew or throw my project to the garbage. It made me rethink the whole concept, and ask myself what was actually my goal and what I actually had to tell. It made me resign to the needless and focus on the important, honest things.

In “Archaia”, as in my previous project, “Screen Memories”, I wanted to try to do something positive out of the sad facts. In “Screen Memories” I also treated the topic of trauma and the memory process, and its relationship with photography. There I focused on Freud’s theory of the Screen Memories (from there the title). According to Sigmund Freud, Screen Memories are a particular kind of childhood memories. He distinguished between apparently indifferent and circumstantial childhood memories and those which he identified as striking, important and emotionally relevant. The latter are covered by those less significant. This can lead to mistakes, falsification or manipulation of the memory.⁹

When I realised that my own childhood memories were so vague and that I almost had no pictures from the time I spent with my father (until I turned twelve years old), I decided to consciously deal with this process by reinterpreting either old pictures of him, staging pictures he took of me, or even creating my own new “screen memories”, in an attempt of manipulating my memory.

This process worked for me as a sort of auto-therapy, in which I treated my past and a difficult time in my life, and also as an experiment, for what I created the pictures that should result in something positive out of all that. And actually, it worked. From the moment I finished the project I had the feeling that I could make a cut and find the peace with whatever happened in the past and with the absence of my father and its manly figure, which I always missed.

9 Freud, Sigmund: *Psychopathology of Everyday Life*, S. Karger, 1904, Chapter IV.

For “Archaia” I wanted to do something similar, but in this case not for me, but for the people that went through that experience. It happened though that in the process of making the pictures of the village, I realised that I also had a traumatic event related to that place that might have been the reason why my creative crisis started. When I was a child I suffered from bullying from the other children that spent the summer there like me.

At the start of the project, I felt unwilling to make projects of the people still living there. I justified this cause with the argument that my project should be “abstract”, not documentary, and the addition of portraits would imply a way too documentary approach, I thought. Per se, it is a valid argument. What I realised later is that every time I was there making pictures, I felt an unexplained anxiety. I wanted to make the pictures so fast as possible, and didn’t gave myself time to reflect and look for images that expressed what I wanted to say. I just took pictures of what I easily saw. This may explain also my tediousness regards the pictures and the project.

After asking a colleague about my project, he told me that what he had the feeling that I had many pictures of death things, and that what he was missing in my project was the “life”. It was at this point when I came to the idea of introducing pictures of the people, of the new village and of things that represented the impact of the reservoir. This should add the aspect of “life”.

When I got there I started to contact the neighbours and I easily got to convince them to let me photograph them. When we took the photographs I realised that just talking to them again and feeling appreciated by them I lost the anxiety and felt that I was confronting a big fear. So it turned out that I, again, made self-therapy out of this project, like in screen memories. And that what was intended to help other, it actually helped me. So just because of that, it has been worth it to do it.

3. The latent image

3.1. The punctum and the “negative” in analog photography

“Latency is a time interval between the stimulation and response, or, from a more general point of view, a time delay between the cause and the effect of some physical change in the system being observed. Latency is physically a consequence of the limited velocity with which any physical interaction can propagate. The magnitude of this velocity is always less than or equal to the speed of light. Therefore, every physical system with any physical separation (distance) between cause and effect will experience some sort of latency, regardless of the nature of stimulation that it has been exposed to.”¹⁰

The old village of Mansilla de la Sierra works for me as a “latent village”, as it is only possible to see it when the water has sunk. The rest of the time, it is hidden below the water, one knows that it is there, and that it will reappear, but cannot be seen.

Roland Barthes used also the term Latency in the process of finding the punctum¹¹.

The punctum as a definite effect of a photograph, not readily locatable, can often only be found after a certain “latency”, that is, after a delay. But this delay is not the exact examination of photography, but looking away or closing the eyes. Sometimes only through the visual separation from the photograph and the purely mental processing, the punctum can be seen. The period from the moment of taking the photograph, then thinking about until recognising the punctum is therefore the latency¹².

10 Latency (engineering) from <http://www.wikipedia.com>

11 Punctum; from lat. punctum = point, smallest size; also “moment”.

Visual phenomenon identified and theorized by Roland Barthes in his study of photography (1980). The point is an often small, initially inconspicuous photographic detail that subtly appeals to the subconscious of the viewer of the photo and ultimately draws his attention.

12 Barthes, Roland: *Camera Lucida*, Hill&Wang, 1980.

Thinking about my working routine, this could explain why I prefer to work with the analogue techniques as with the digital ones. I need to leave a certain period of time from the moment I make the pictures till the moment I get to look at them. I need to give the pictures and my perception a “break”. And then, after some weeks, sometimes months, I am able to look at them and see them in a very different way as in the moment I pressed the shutter. I always thought that it had to do with the fact that this way, the remembering of the image I was taking was still remaining a moment in my life experience. In the case of digital pictures, in the very moment that I looked at the photo I had taken on the viewer, it was converted for me in a picture, in something material. In the case of the analogue ones, the moment of taking the picture was still in my memory, I hadn’t lost it yet. And when after some time I look at the prints or negatives, my mind had the time to process it and it felt as if I looked at that motive anew.

I also realised that from a moment, I stopped scanning my pictures. I was still getting them developed and printed, but I didn’t share them with anyone. I have done this for five years now. So I have tons of boxes full with analogue pictures, mostly taken with a point&shoot camera that no one besides me has seen. I wondered why. And I came to the conclusion that maybe, I wanted to forget those moments. If I didn’t show that pictures to anyone, it would be as if they didn’t existed. As if that moments never happened. Perhaps I needed five years to be able to confront them. Because now I feel that I am ready to dig them out, and actually I will use them for my next project “Viktoria”.

Back to Freud, he also formulated an analogy between the developing process of analogue photographs and that of the becoming conscious of psychic processes:

“A rough, but rather adequate analogy of this supposition of the ‘conscious activity’ to the ‘unconscious’ offers the field of ordinary photography. The first stage of photography is the negative; every photographic image has to undergo the “negative process,” and some of these negatives, which have well passed the test, are admitted to the “positive process” that ends with the picture”.¹³

13 Freud, Sigmund: *Some Remarks on the Concept of the Unconscious in Psychoanalysis*, in:

Here the most important part is the difference between the “unconscious” and the “conscious” that Freud compares to the negative (the film) and the positive (the printed picture). The concept of the latent image, the exposed but undeveloped images (and thus still invisible) finds its equivalent here. Based on the assumption that photography is privileged to “accurately” depict reality, the importance of photography for the accurate reproduction and storage of the past is quite interesting. This is also why I realised the magnitude from the power of photographs, and that in the case of Mansilla de la Sierra, the photos will be the only remaining witnesses at some point.

Walter Benjamin also realised the power in pictures and he emphasized in the “auratic” character of ‘old’ photographs, which gives them their specific power and beauty.¹⁴

He distinguishes these from the ‘newer’ snapshots.

Contrary to the appreciation of the auratic images, he comes, however, to the following conclusion:

“ The true picture of the past scurries past. Only as a picture, never to see you again at the moment of its recognizability, the past has to be recorded.

[...] Because it is an irretrievable image of the past, with every present threatens to disappear, who did not recognize himself as meant in it”.¹⁵

Walter Benjamin thought about the ability of photography to store the past to be problematic¹⁶, but regarding the processes of psychoanalysis, he accepted the chance it offers to retrospectively visualise “the optical-unconscious” and to capture impressions that do not enter consciousness at the moment of their happening.

Mitscherlich, Alexander / Richards, Angela / Strachey, James (ed.): Sigmund Freud Study Edition, Volume III, Psychology of the Unconscious. Frankfurt am Main: S. Fischer Verlag, pp. 25-37, 1975

14 Benjamin, Walter: *On the concept of history*, in: *Collected writings*. ed. by Rolf Tiedemann, Rolf / Schweppenhäuser, Hermann, Vol. 1.2. Frankfurt am Main: Suhrkamp, 691-704. P. 695, 1990

15 Quoted after Aßmann, Aleida: *Fotografie und Geister in der Gegenwartskunst*, Bielefeld, 2014.

16 Ibid..

3.2. The Post-Memory

Photography has a direct connection to the past. On the one hand, it is a proof that something once existed, but also that what is being seen is no longer there. This expresses two different functions of photography: the documentary and the memorial function.

In the documentary function, photography works as a store of evidence: it is like a witness of the inaccessible past and can be used as an object or means for the subsequent reconstruction of narratives, arguments and proofs.

In the memorial function, photography functions as an emotional memory: it retains a visual trace of something or someone who is no longer there; is shared by several people who are related to the photographed person or thing; captures the transience of time, helping to ensure that something does not fall into oblivion.

Besides these two functions, Mariane Hirsch also speaks of the concept of “post-memory”, in which the status of photography shifts in the time dimension: it makes a difference between the people who have suffered traumatic events (the first generation) and are directly related to the depicted persons (or things) and to those who do not have this direct connection, but have only received this traumatic event through narratives. This creates a distortion of the narrative, according to Hirsch, because the connection to an object or a source is not mediated by memory, but by an imaginative investment and creation.

As Mariane Hirsch writes, “Post-memory characterizes the experience of those who grew up dominated by narratives that preceded their birth, whose own stories are evacuated by stories of the previous generation shaped by traumatic events that can be understood or recreated”.¹⁷

I am particularly interested in this last sentence “stories of the previous generation shaped by traumatic events that can be understood or recreated” as it deals with the topic of my Master’s thesis: How the visual repetition of a traumatic event can be helpful or, in the contrary, inconvenient.

17 Hirsch, *Family Frames*, S. 22

In my case, the traumatic event is the flooding of the village and the resulting forced resettlement of the inhabitants. The first generation in this case are my grandparents, who could share this facts with us. They lived in this village and they know the people in the archive pictures, as well as the places. But they have more or less repressed this topic and do not want to talk about it. The second generation includes their children, this is my mother, aunts & uncles who have more disposition to talk about it. However, this traumatic experience did not directly hit them. They speak of narratives or pictures of which they have have seen or heard about. Thus, after Hirsch, they can not really fully understand or recapitulate what happened.

Following the example of the book “The Lost” by Hans-Ulrich Treichels, Assmann argues that the photograph of the lost child takes on a larger dimension because it is the last indication of his existence. That is the only thing left to the parents about their presence. If this image were lost, it would be like the second “death” of the Son. The mother, when she secretly sees the lost child again, she cannot accept how he looks like. Her memory of him is shaped and captured as the child in the photo. But for the surviving brother he looks like the image of a spirit. He imagines a sort of doppelganger who looks like himself. He also realises this when he looks at the picture of him.

To aspect of the documentary and the memorial functions of photography, Aleida Assmann adds another one: the “memento-mori” function. The term “memento-mori” comes from Latin and means “Remember that you will die”. In the process, photography is described as a reminder of death: the moment in which something has been photographed enters the past immediately. After the shutter is pressed, the “mortification” of that moment is captured forever. What can be seen in a photograph will never look the same again. It shows the moment of the condition of this person or thing at the precise moment and in the particular place.

One could also wonder “What happens to the photos of someone who died?”. In order to argue about this “memento-mori” function, Assmann uses the work of the artist Christian Boltanski, who, as she puts it, “made the overlapping of documentary and memorial func-

tion of photography the content of his art like no other”¹⁸.

Boltanski works primarily with private portrait photographs, which he does not do himself, but finds somewhere: From the press, archives or flea markets. So he has no direct relation to these people. If you look at his installations, you have to think precisely about this “memento-mori” aspect of photography and its relation to the oppositions “death / life”, “forgetting / remembering”, “absent / present”. The images are shown without any kind of information or contextualization, so they lose their meaning. However, the people shown there are not to be “recognized”. He is more concerned with a staging of the forgetting, not with memory, but also with the psychological, cultural and social recharging of photographs. Through the processing and the way in which these images are transformed and shown, he allows the observer to approach them, through the inner images that we all know and the resulting perception. According to Assmann, this way of dealing with images would be the so-called “post-post-memory”: the processing of a traumatic event by a third generation, who has been aware of this event through the second-generation narration and creation (post-memory). In this sense, Boltanski creates his own after-memory. In the case of my master’s thesis I also belong to this “third generation”, because I also try to work in the same way. With her term “post-memory” Hirsch refers to the transition from the generation of “experience” to the later generations, who still participate in the living circulation of the communicative memory. Outside of this lively framework of interaction and communication, the memorial value of photography is extinguished, thereby repeatedly changing its status: “This is the transition from the representation of a person to a ghost to a pure picture”.¹⁹

After my artistic approach and the theory of A. Assmann I find that the archive images of people in my master’s thesis, who have experienced this traumatic event, for me as “pure pictures” act. Without reference to these people, the pictures mean nothing to me, even if they are known to me. But when I regard those images before any manipulation or post-processing, they seem to me more like ghosts than when I look at the abstracted ones.

18 Quoted after Assmann, Aleida: *Fotografie und Geister in der Gegenwartskunst*, Bielefeld, 2014.

19 Ibid.

Christian Boltanski : *Grande Réserve, La fête du Pourim*,
1989

4. Archaeography

“Archaeography”, after the Ancient Greek *arkhaiográphos* (“the writing of antiquities”), discipline for publishing treatises of any antiquity or antiquities”.²⁰

After getting some distance from my first approach to the topic of this paper, I realised that I had been focusing too much on the trauma and the psychological consequences of the historical events, and that it might have a negative effect on me and the project. Thus I tried to look for a more positive perspective and came to the idea of relating my topic to archaeology and the relationship between archaeology and photography and between “reality” and fiction. I found a very interesting paper from Michael Shanks and Connie Svabo about an hybrid between photography and archaeology, which I will explain in the next under chapter.

4.1. The reliability of the photograph as a witness to events and places

Not only photography and psychoanalysis were two disciplines that developed hand in hand at the same time in the mid nineteenth century, archaeology did too. The three of them indicate marking moments of modernity.

An archaeological excavation could not be conceived without the photographic record of what has been found, since in order to find remains, one must dig, that is, destroy; and everything that is destroyed has to be documented before continuing digging.

The photographs become evidence or proofs, from which it is possible to “rebuild” the previous state or the missing parts of objects, ruins or traces. I like to think that in archeology what is found is as important as what is no longer there, what no longer exists, the invisible. From the remains of what is left, we try to reconstruct what no longer can be seen. When we look at a photograph, we could think about “what happened here?”; but also about the moment before the photographs was taken “what has happened here before?”;

20 From Wikipedia: <https://en.wiktionary.org/wiki/archaeography>

and about the near future “what could happen here?”.

A photograph offers infinite possibilities to interpret what is being seen. A place that is photographed becomes a possible scenario for many different stories. And this made me wonder if the lack of information in an image makes us being more curious about what actually happened.

Here an excerpt of the paper about Archaeography:

“The connection between archaeology and photography is more than that photography simply offered an effective technique of illustration and documentation. Antiquarians had long explored crucial questions of how to represent their interests in ancient artefacts, ruins, remains, and monuments, through illustrated publications, maps and diagrams.”²¹ [...]

“These questions of media and representation connect with deep epistemological concerns regarding the construction of knowledge of the past on the basis of ruins and remains. There are ontological concerns too, regarding, for example the very nature of the historical past. Can an assemblage of artefacts represent the essential being of an historical epoch? Are tangible artefacts more of an historical reality than verbal testimony? Similar questions apply to photography, regarding, for example, the reliability of the photograph as a witness to events and places.”²²

In this regard, we could think that there is more than the technical or mediating connection between photography and archaeology (for example documenting or preserving), but also that there is a common structure or even an ontology: the study of “being”.

As ontology tries to study which things do exist or are said to exist, and how these things can be clustered, connected through a hierarchy and delimited by what they have in com-

21 Quoted after: M.Shanks & C. Svabo: *Archaeology and photography: a pragmatology*, Routledge, 2013

22 M.Shanks & C. Svabo: *Archaeology and photography: a pragmatology*, Routledge, 2013

mon or their differences I can take this case as the “ontology” of two villages. Also regarding the term “archaeography” from the Greek “to archaia” (old things) plus “graphos” (inscription), I decided to take it as the title of this work, because it exactly expresses what I am trying to do: to recollect every visual reminiscence that I can find about this villages. I am creating my own archeological archive: collecting, documenting, depicting of site and architecture, capturing things that might no longer be with us. On the ontological aspect, the thing that all these things have in common, is that they all have or will disappear. It is thus a project about disappearing. Everything will disappear at some point. It is just a matter of time.

This might sound obvious, but when I realised that my grandma was also disappearing (dying), I understood that not only the ruins will disappear. From the moment that my grandma will be dead, I would lose the connection to that place and everything will also disappear for me: the visits, her house, her hens and her vegetable plot (from which I ate the best eggs and vegetables of my life), the landscape view from her window, everything. Even the relationship to my family, as she is the person who connects us all.

This lead me to think of this project as an archive for the future. An archive where I can keep photographs of everything related to it. If my previous project “screen memories” was about creating my own memories because of the lack of pictures, this one is about preserving every single thing left so that I can remember it in the future. This archive might be also useful for future generations when everything is already gone.

At first I wondered if it was justifiable to make an “archive” about this. When I asked a friend who is an archeologist, “how do you decide which things or places are justified to be researched about?”, she told me “anything can be justified to be researched, if you have a reason to study it. Each archeologist focuses on a certain period of history or a certain folk, but everything can be taken in account.” So I thought that my reasons my be enough to realise it.

I then decided to start my work as an “archeographer” instead of just a photographer,

documenting everything. Anything can be of photographic or archeological interest. The aspect of imagining multiple scenarios in a photograph or a place could be determined as forensic: “This forensic character of site requires constant vigilance and unceasing effort under an anxiety to document as much as possible, because we don’t actually know what is, has, or might be going on, and may never know.”²³

Thinking about nowadays, it’s a fact that there is the tendency in the social media to photograph absolutely everything around us, because our smart phones and the internet, who are our inseparable companions, allow this to us, 24/7. It feels like we moved forward from an attempt of “documenting” more to a “sharing” attitude through the social media. It is not anymore so important what we see or what we document, the real aim is to be seen. The bigger the personal archive, the more chances it has to be seen and thus to be liked or commented. It’s more about recognition and feeling valuable.

23 Archaeology&photography: a pragmatology”; Michael Shanks&Connie Svabo, 2013, Routledge

4.2 The actuality & the duration

There are two temporal aspects that we can find in archeology which could also be related to photography:

-the “Actuality”: the kairoitic (specific and located) association of the past in the present (something found, excavated, inspected or documented)

-and the “Duration”: the persistence of the material past (remains, ruins and traces).²⁴

This would be, translated into photography, the moment in which something is photographed (the “Actuality”) and the presentation of the material photograph, for example, in an exhibition (the “Duration”).

We can then consider archives, museums and galleries as the perpetrators of the “Duration” of photography, and of archeology. Also the prefix “arche-”, present in the terms Architecture, Archive and Archaeology means in Greek “beginning, origin, foundation, source, first principle, central location and origin of power, authority, sovereignty. Archives are (for Shanks and Svabo), all about narratives of origin, identity and belonging, and the politics of ownership, organization, access and use”.²⁵

I find here a connection to the text from Bruno Latour “Visualisation and cognition: Drawing things together” in the chapter where he tells the story about La Pérouse and the map of Sakhalin:

“La Pérouse travels through the Pacific for Louis XVI with the explicit mission of bringing back a better map. One day, landing on what he calls

24 “While duration is an aspect of materiality and curation (the photograph needs a certain amount of care for it to survive), kairos or actuality is specific and located, the temporal aspect of a site specific, architectural arrangement or assemblage, as we have just described. A persistent moment, the subject of photo work, the material photograph presents a return of the moment of capture, in a kind of haunting. A photograph says—this was all here then, and is with us still now. “Archaeology and photography: a pragmatology”; Michael Shanks & Connie Svabo, 2013, Routledge.

25 M.Shanks & C. Svabo: *Archaeology and photography: a pragmatology*, Routledge, 2013

Sakhalin he meets with Chinese and tries to learn from them whether Sakhalin is an island or a peninsula. To his great surprise the Chinese understand geography quite well. An older man stands up and draws a map of his island on the sand with the scale and the details needed by La Pérouse. Another, who is younger, sees that the rising tide will soon erase the map and picks up one of La Pérouse's notebooks to draw the map again with a pencil . . . [...]

In other words, it is not perception which is at stake in this problem of visualization and cognition. New inscriptions, and new! ways of perceiving them, are the results of something deeper. If you wish to go out of your way and come back heavily equipped so as to force others to go out of their ways, the main problem to solve is that of mobilization. You have to go and to come back with the "things" if your moves are not to be wasted. But the "things" have to be able to withstand the return trip without withering away. Further requirements: the "things" you gathered and displaced have to be presentable all at once to those you want to convince and who did not go there. In sum, you have to invent objects which have the properties of being mobile but also immutable, presentable, readable and combinable with one another."²⁶

The "actuality" of that map was the moment it was drawn by the chinese man. The "durability" was the act of letting him draw it on a piece of paper, which could transport the map in an unaltered form. It is this durability of immutable inscriptions (photographs between them) which gives them the power of being political: they show what once was in front of the camera, and this image/message can travel the world, get to many people and transport an original information, that will be trusted. I guess the problem comes then with the given context, in which way theses inscriptions are used, showed or presented, what also represents an alteration of meaning.

26 Latour, Bruno in Kuklick H.: *Knowledge and Society Studies in the Sociology of Culture Past and Present*, Jai Press vol. 6, pp. 1-40

5. Photography and fiction

5.1. I photograph to forget

“Forgetting is such an important function of memory as remembering.” Vilém Flusser.²⁷

Joan Fontcuberta has dealt for a long time with the topic of photography and reality (or not-reality) and memory. In his book “The kiss of Judas” we can find a passage where he tells about this quote from Norberto Bobbio from his essay *De Senectute*: “We are what we remember”.²⁸

Me, like Fontcuberta, also support this theory, by which “both our notion of the real and the essence of our individual identity depends on the memory. We are nothing but memory. The photograph, then, is a fundamental activity to define ourselves that opens a double way of asceticism towards self-affirmation and knowledge.”

Silverberg suggested that, in fact, it is the discrimination of memory and, in the end, forgetting is what which allows us to aspire to be happy.²⁹

I could say that I photograph to forget. This supports also my attempt to get to the truth, or to create my own truth through my photographs. Actually, it is not to remember what I’m trying to achieve, but to be able to forget.

By selecting what I photograph, I create new memories, which allow me (or even forces me) to forget other ones. And for this, like I had commented in the chapter about post-memory, a certain amount of fiction is necessary.

I needed a part of fiction to be able to get some distance from the project and make it more universal. So this was actually the real issue: how do I make this personal story into a project that gets the attention of viewers that have nothing to do with it?

27 Flusser, Vilém: *On Memory (Electronic or Otherwise)*, The MIT Press, 1990

28 Bobbio, Norberto: *De Senectute*, Taurus, 1997

29 Fontcuberta, Joan: *The kiss of Judas*, Gustavo Gili, 1989

As Roland Barthes said: “A photograph’s punctum is that accident which pricks me (but also bruises me, is poignant to me).”³⁰ I tried to find this punctum, that may be also the punctum for other people. I found it firstly in archeology and the mix of art and science. But also on a very actual topic: the climate change.

During the last 3 years I’ve seen how the climate conditions have changed, and also how this affects the landscape: the seasons changed, the temperatures have radicalised, what makes the drought worse and that natural catastrophes arise due to torrential rains. All this effects will cause a faster disappearing of the ruins and actually also of the earth. So this is how I try to integrate my project into a more universal and more important issue. And also a projection into the future.

5.2. The good photographer is the one who lies well the truth

“Every photograph is a fiction that is presented as a truth against what they have instilled in us, against what we usually think, the photo always lies, it lies instinctively, it lies because its nature does not allow it to do anything else. But the important thing is not that inevitable lie. The important thing is how the photographer uses it, to what intentions does it serve? The important thing, in short, is control exerted by the photographer to impose and address ethics to a lie. The good photographer is the one who lies well the truth”.³¹

There is a funny story about a photograph from Arthur Rothstein from 1936. At that time he was working for the Farm Security Administration and was sent to make pictures at the agricultural communities impoverished in the Dust Bowl. One day he discovered a steer skull in South Dakota and began staging several pictures with different backgrounds and lighting with it, specially playing with in the texture of the cracked earth against the bone. When he sent the picture to Associated Press, an editor separated this image from

30 Barthes, Roland: *Camera Lucida*, Hill & Wang, 1990

31 Fontcuberta, Joan: *The kiss of Judas*, Gustavo Gili, 1989

its experimental context and published it accompanied by a caption that was not the one provided by Rothsteins, and so the picture became the icon of the increasingly severe drought happening in the US, even if the photograph wasn't depicting that in reality, and made thousands of farmers to leave their land. After the press discovered that there were different staged photos of that skull and that it was actually a fraud, they were immediately labelled as government propaganda, specially by various conservative newspapers around the country which opposed President Roosevelt's New Deal policies.³²

This is a good example about manipulation in photography, reminding us that we still have not found a comfortable resolution regarding the relationships between photography, truth, and propaganda.

I found quite interesting that I actually made a very similar picture of a tree root that looks like a skull or a antler (before i knew about this story) , which depicts something very similar: the attempting drought in Spain. But in my case it is clear from the start that it is my statement, not something I want to convince to, but maybe to bring attention to it. Another fun fact about the story of Mansilla de la Sierra is that when the new village was going to be inaugurated official public act, you can imagine that most of the people there weren't actually happy or in the mood to celebrate. This is why Franco made neighbours from other villages go there to make the press photographs of the event look more full of people and joy. A lie that woul bring Franco's colonization and water-reservoirs-strategy more reputation and recognition. I imagine the faces of the people reading that newspaper and thinking how lucky those people were or at least looking like.

For "Archaia" I decided finally not to make fictional images, but to show them in a fictional context: the context of science and archeology. All the images I've made for this project are actually from existing things or places. For the "fictional part", I've changed their look in the postproduction so they seem from an archeological study or similar. On some of them I've added transparencies so that they look as if they were vanishing, and

32 Hirsch, Robert: *Seizing the Light: A Social & Aesthetic History of Photography*

on other ones there is some visual attempts of imagining how the archive of the future would look like. I am then trying to make the viewer believe that this is actually an archeological study of general interest, even though it might be only for me. Also in the installation I play with how Museums show this kind of historical material and also try to make objects out of the photographs that represent “objects”, as the “objects” have already (fictionally) disappeared, so I can only show photographs from nonexistent things.

Arthur Rothstein: *Skull*, Badlands, South Dakota, 1936

6. Conclusion

“Art is a lie that allows us to tell the truth” Pablo Picasso.

Everything is memory. Memory recalls events and things, photography allows us to recall those memories, but also to create them. As photographers we dig out remembrances like archeologists dig out stones. Science needs physical material proofs (“immutable mobiles”) that allow to transport the discovered facts to others and make them believable. But as our brain also creates inexistent or fake facts in our memories, we can also create photographs of inexistent or fake things (or from actually real things to which we change the context) which we could contemplate as real, or use them to create and recall a reality that we would like to live. For example in the process of confronting a story like the one of Mansilla de la Sierra and the pursue to understand and to overcome it.

Archaeology of the invisible (Archaia)

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